

STROBE checklist for: Evaluation of the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effect of sublingual glutathione on COPD patients: an observational study

	Item No.	Recommendation	Included
Title and abstract	1	(a) Indicate the study's design with a commonly used term in the title or the abstract	Yes
		(b) Provide in the abstract an informative and balanced summary of what was done and what was found	Yes
Introduction			
Background/rationale	2	Explain the scientific background and rationale for the investigation being reported	Yes
Objectives	3	State specific objectives, including any prespecified hypotheses	Yes
Methods			
Study design	4	Present key elements of study design early in the paper	Yes
Setting	5	Describe the setting, locations, and relevant dates, including periods of recruitment, exposure, follow-up, and data collection	Yes
Participants	6	(a) <i>Cohort study</i> —Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants. Describe methods of follow-up <i>Case-control study</i> —Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of case ascertainment and control selection. Give the rationale for the choice of cases and controls <i>Cross-sectional study</i> —Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants	Yes
		(b) <i>Cohort study</i> —For matched studies, give matching criteria and number of exposed and unexposed <i>Case-control study</i> —For matched studies, give matching criteria and the number of controls per case	Yes
Variables	7	Clearly define all outcomes, exposures, predictors, potential confounders, and effect modifiers. Give diagnostic criteria, if applicable	Yes
Data sources/ measurement	8*	For each variable of interest, give sources of data and details of methods of assessment (measurement). Describe comparability of assessment methods if there is more than one group	Yes
Bias	9	Describe any efforts to address potential sources of bias	Yes
Study size	10	Explain how the study size was arrived at	

Quantitative variables	11	Explain how quantitative variables were handled in the analyses. If applicable, describe which groupings were chosen and why	Yes
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Statistical methods	12	(a) Describe all statistical methods, including those used to control for confounding	Yes
		(b) Describe any methods used to examine subgroups and interactions	Yes
		(c) Explain how missing data were addressed	Yes
		(d) <i>Cohort study</i> —If applicable, explain how loss to follow-up was addressed <i>Case-control study</i> —If applicable, explain how matching of cases and controls was addressed <i>Cross-sectional study</i> —If applicable, describe analytical methods taking account of sampling strategy	Yes
		(e) Describe any sensitivity analyses	
Participants	13*	(a) Report numbers of individuals at each stage of study—eg numbers potentially eligible, examined for eligibility, confirmed eligible, included in the study, completing follow-up, and analysed	Yes
		(b) Give reasons for non-participation at each stage	No
		(c) Consider use of a flow diagram	No
Descriptive data	14*	(a) Give characteristics of study participants (eg demographic, clinical, social) and information on exposures and potential confounders	
		(b) Indicate number of participants with missing data for each variable of interest	Yes
		(c) <i>Cohort study</i> —Summarise follow-up time (eg, average and total amount)	No
Outcome data	15*	<i>Cohort study</i> —Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures over time	Yes
		<i>Case-control study</i> —Report numbers in each exposure category, or summary measures of exposure	
		<i>Cross-sectional study</i> —Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures	Yes
Main results	16	(a) Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-adjusted estimates and their precision (eg, 95% confidence interval). Make clear which confounders were adjusted for and why they were included	Yes
		(b) Report category boundaries when continuous variables were categorized	Yes
		(c) If relevant, consider translating estimates of relative risk into absolute risk for a meaningful time period	Yes

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Other analyses	17	Report other analyses done—eg analyses of subgroups and interactions, and sensitivity analyses	No
Key results	18	Summarise key results with reference to study objectives	Yes
Limitations	19	Discuss limitations of the study, taking into account sources of potential bias or imprecision. Discuss both direction and magnitude of any potential bias	Yes
Interpretation	20	Give a cautious overall interpretation of results considering objectives, limitations, multiplicity of analyses, results from similar studies, and other relevant evidence	Yes
Generalisability	21	Discuss the generalisability (external validity) of the study results	Yes
Other information			
Funding	22	Give the source of funding and the role of the funders for the present study and, if applicable, for the original study on which the present article is based	No funds

*Give information separately for cases and controls in case-control studies and, if applicable, for exposed and unexposed groups in cohort and cross-sectional studies.

Note: An Explanation and Elaboration article discusses each checklist item and gives methodological background and published examples of transparent reporting. The STROBE checklist is best used in conjunction with this article (freely available on the Web sites of PLoS Medicine at <http://www.plosmedicine.org/>, Annals of Internal Medicine at <http://www.annals.org/>, and Epidemiology at <http://www.epidem.com/>). Information on the STROBE Initiative is available at www.strobe-statement.org.